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Green Hive Objective:

GreenHive's primary goal is to **foster sustainability** in education by encouraging **collaboration**, driving **innovation**, and maintaining a **strong commitment** to environmental awareness. Through this approach, we aim to empower both educators and students to take actionable steps toward sustainability, while promoting a collective responsibility for a healthier planet.

COMBS TRAINING

>>> COLLABORATION WITH EDUCATORS

We've recently conducted several online workshops with the representatives of the Comb, our partners from Spain, Italy, Ireland, Romania, and Greece. These workshops focused on **how sustainability can be integrated into everyday classroom practices**. Each partner hosted a session, creating a space for open discussions, sharing of best practices, and brainstorming new ideas for sustainability education.

Key Points:

- Exchange of ideas between Comb representatives from different EU countries and experts.
- We received valuable feedback and suggestions from teachers on how to improve the project.
- A practical approach on how students can become aware of their ecological footprint.

DEVELOPMENT OF EDUCATIONAL RESOURCES

European Sustainability Competence Framework

This framework defines essential sustainability competences in four key areas: **embodying sustainability values**, **embracing complexity**, **envisioning a sustainable future**, and **acting for sustainability**. It serves as a reference for developing educational initiatives and resources related to environmental sustainability.

Competency-Specific Resources

Tailored educational materials are provided for each GreenComp competence area:

- **Embodying Sustainability Values:** Resources that help students engage with real-world sustainability challenges and develop skills in collaboration and problem-solving.
- **Embracing Complexity in Sustainability:** Resources that guide students through the complexities of sustainability issues, encouraging deep understanding and critical thinking.
- **Envisioning a Sustainable Future:** Tools and activities for helping students imagine and plan for sustainable solutions.
- **Acting for Sustainability:** Resources focused on practical actions that students can take toward a more sustainable future through interactive workshops and project-based exercises.

Language version:

ENGLISH

ROMANIAN

ITALIAN

GREEK

SPANISH

LEARNING METHODOLOGIES

The **Learning Methodologies** section offers practical, step-by-step approaches to foster sustainability education. It includes guidelines for creating Open Space Discussions, Workshop Scenarios and Project-Based Learning. These methodologies are designed to engage learners and develop key sustainability competencies.

- **Open Space Discussions.** Where students, educators, and other stakeholders collaborate and share ideas.
- **Workshop Scenarios.** provide interactive, hands-on activities that promote active learning through case studies, role plays, and discussions.
- **Project-Based Learning** encourages students to solve real-world environmental challenges, enhancing their problem-solving and critical thinking skills.

VIRTUAL KNOWLEDGE FAIR

»»» GLOBAL CONNECTION FOR THE EXCHANGE OF **SUSTAINABILITY KNOWLEDGE**

We recently hosted the **Virtual Knowledge Fair**, an online event that brought together VET educators, trainers, and professionals to share knowledge, experiences, and **best practices** in sustainability education.

It also provided a platform to exchange resources and tools for integrating sustainability into educational programs.

[Visit the Virtual Knowledge Fair](#)

NEXT STEPS...

Looking ahead, the GreenHive project has exciting plans for the upcoming months, including:

An European Contest:

The "**Sustainability: New Perspectives For A Wicked Problem**" competition, part of the Green Hive project, encourages participants to co-create sustainability solutions in vocational education and training (VET). It promotes collaboration across Europe, empowers learners, and aims to share best practices. The competition also supports the GreenComp framework, involves external stakeholders, and recognizes top entries with awards.

The Development of a Platform:

The "Green Hive" Platform aims to **connect 15 local hubs** and improve sustainability competencies for 225 students through transnational collaboration.

It enhances educators' ability to prepare learners for the green transition and circular economy.

Key features include:

- Educational resources
- Tools for activity co-creation and contest management
- Event creation
- Green Combs profiles and an interactive map
- Networking spaces
- Multilingual support (EN, EL, ES, IT, RO).

The platform also offers technical assistance and onboarding support.